

Vehicle Insurance Claim Fraud Detection

Keerthi U

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
keerthiu798@gmail.com

Rini Kurian

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
rinikurian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Vehicle insurance claim fraud poses a significant challenge to the insurance industry, resulting in substantial financial losses annually. Fraudulent activities range from staged accidents to falsified claims for damages or injuries that never occurred. In response, insurance companies are actively seeking effective strategies to detect and prevent fraud. This abstract explores innovative approaches for detecting vehicle insurance claim fraud, with a focus on leveraging data analytics and machine learning algorithms. By analyzing patterns within vast datasets encompassing claim histories, vehicle and driver information, and accident details, insurers can unveil potential instances of fraud. Machine learning algorithms, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), offer promising capabilities in automating the detection process. These algorithms utilize advanced mathematical techniques to identify intricate patterns and anomalies indicative of fraudulent behavior.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Support Vector Machine, Fraud Detection System

I. INTRODUCTION

Insurance fraud poses a significant threat to the financial stability of the vehicle insurance industry, resulting in substantial losses for insurers annually. Fraudulent claims, ranging from staged accidents to fabricated damages or injuries, impose a heavy burden on insurers and compromise the trust of policyholders. To mitigate this risk and safeguard their financial health, insurers are increasingly turning to advanced technologies, such as data analytics and machine learning algorithms, to develop robust fraud detection systems.

This introduction highlights the importance of implementing a vehicle insurance claim fraud detection system as a proactive measure against fraudulent activities. By harnessing cutting-edge technologies, insurers can effectively identify patterns within claims data, enabling them to detect suspicious activity and investigate further to distinguish legitimate claims from fraudulent ones. Key data sources, including claim histories, vehicle and driver information, and accident details, serve as valuable inputs for the fraud detection system, facilitating the identification of potential instances of fraud. While the benefits of deploying a fraud detection system are substantial, it's essential to acknowledge the challenges associated with implementation. Developing and implementing a customized fraud detection system demands a significant investment of time, resources, and expertise. Collaboration between insurance companies, data scientists, and technology experts is imperative to tailor the system to specific needs and address unique challenges within the insurance landscape.

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II. RELATED WORKS

Reddy et al. (2020) presented a study on fraud detection in insurance claims using machine learning [1]. Their research demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning models in identifying fraudulent insurance claims, thereby helping insurance companies mitigate financial losses. The study provides insights into the application of machine learning techniques for fraud detection in the insurance sector.

Prabhu et al. (2020) proposed a framework for insurance claim fraud detection [2] using machine learning algorithms. Their study highlighted the importance of feature selection and model evaluation techniques in building robust fraud detection systems. The framework provides a systematic approach for implementing machine learning-based fraud detection solutions in the insurance industry.

Sharma et al. (2021) conducted research on the detection and prediction of insurance fraud using machine learning and deep learning techniques [3]. Their study emphasized the role of advanced machine learning algorithms in improving the accuracy of fraud detection systems. The research contributes to the development of more efficient fraud detection mechanisms in the insurance sector.

Somwanshi et al. (2021) investigated fraud detection in the insurance sector using various machine learning techniques [4]. They identified key factors contributing to insurance fraud and developed predictive models to detect fraudulent claims effectively. The study offers insights into the application of machine learning for combating insurance fraud.

Sharma et al. (2021) proposed a deep learning-based approach for fraud detection in the insurance sector [5]. Their research demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning algorithms in capturing complex patterns associated with fraudulent activities. The study presents a novel method for enhancing fraud detection capabilities in insurance claims processing.

Aher et al. (2022) Aher et al. conducted research on fraud detection in the insurance sector using machine learning techniques [6]. They emphasized the need for scalable and efficient algorithms capable of handling large volumes of insurance data.

Pawar et al. (2022) Pawar et al. investigated machine learning techniques for fraud detection in the insurance sector [7]. Their study focused on the development of robust and interpretable machine learning models to identify fraudulent insurance claims accurately.

III. METHODOLOGY

The primary philosophy underlying the field of car insurance claim fraud detection is the identification and prevention of fraudulent insurance claims through the application of cutting-edge technologies and data analytics. This philosophy highlights the significance of utilizing predictive modeling and machine learning algorithms to evaluate vast amounts of claims data and find trends and abnormalities that might point to fraud. It also emphasizes how crucial it is for fraud detection systems to be updated and trained on a regular basis in order to accommodate new fraud strategies.

A. Data Collection

Kaggle is a Google subsidiary that provides users with an online platform for downloading and sharing data sets. In addition, it gives users the ability to create models in a setting that is primarily web-based and data-science focused. In essence, it's a community for aficionados in data science and machine learning to get data to work, as well as a platform to showcase their work. It also organizes competitions where participants can improve their machine learning (ML) abilities and obtain some helpful research suggestions. The dataset we utilized to train our model was obtained from Kaggle.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import plotly.express as px
import plotly.graph_objects as go
import plotly.figure_factory as ff

import os
for dirname, _, filenames in os.walk('insurance_claim'):
    for filename in filenames:
        print(os.path.join(dirname, filename))
df = pd.read_csv("E:/S2_network/project4/pythonProject/insurance_claim/insurance_claims.csv")
```

B. Data Preprocessing Data Cleaning: Unwanted columns are dropped

```
df.drop(labels="c39",axis=1,inplace=True)

print("Number of Rows",df.shape[0])
print("Number of Columns",df.shape[1])
```

- Handling Missing Values: Checking and handling any missing values that may exist.

```
styled_desc_obj
styled_desc

missing_values = df.isnull().sum()

# Print the number of missing values in each column
print(missing_values)
```

C. Exploratory Data Analysis: Visualizing data using Seaborn and Matplotlib to gain insights into the dataset.

```
inc_ser = pd.DataFrame(df.groupby(["incident_severity"])["fraud_reported"].value_counts().reset_index(name="Total"))
inc_ser = inc_ser.sort_values(by="Total", ascending=False)
inc_ser.rename(columns={"incident_severity": "incidentseverity", "fraud_reported": "fraudreported", "inplace=True"})

fig1 = go.Figure(data=[go.Table(header=dict(values=list(inc_ser.columns),
align="left",
line_color="black",
fill_color="#62F939"),
cells=dict(values=[inc_ser.incidentseverity, inc_ser.fraudreported, inc_ser.Total],
align="left",
line_color="black",
fill_color="#A4F8C"))])

fig1.show()

make = pd.DataFrame(df.groupby('auto_make')['fraud_reported'].value_counts().reset_index(name="Total"))
make=make[make["fraud_reported"]=="Y"]
make.sort_values(by="Total",ascending=False,inplace=True)

df["collision_type"]=df["collision_type"].fillna(df["collision_type"].mode()[0])
df["property_damage"]=df["property_damage"].fillna(df["property_damage"].mode()[0])
df["police_report_available"]=df["police_report_available"].fillna(df["police_report_available"].mode()[0])

#Total Fraud in this dataset:
```

D. Data Splitting : Splitting the dataset into training and testing sets.

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(*arrays, X, y, test_size = 0.25)

print(len(X_train))
print(len(X_test))
```

E. Data visualize : Data visualization involves the graphical representation of data to facilitate understanding, analysis, and interpretation. It is a crucial aspect of data analysis and plays a vital role in extracting insights, identifying patterns, and communicating findings effectively

Police report vs state visualize data

F. Detection Function : Create a function to make insurance fraud predictions.

```
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier

knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors = 30)
knn.fit(X_train, y_train)

y_pred = knn.predict(X_train)
y_pred

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
import seaborn as sns

# Calculate the confusion matrix
conf_matrix = confusion_matrix(y_train, y_pred)

# Plot the confusion matrix
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
sns.heatmap(conf_matrix, annot=True, fmt='d', cmap='Blues', cbar=False)
plt.xlabel('Predicted Labels')
plt.ylabel('True Labels')
plt.title('Confusion Matrix')
plt.show()
```

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, the implementation of a Vehicle Insurance Claim Fraud Detection system is imperative for identifying and thwarting fraudulent claims, thereby safeguarding insurance companies from financial losses. Leveraging machine learning and data analysis, the system meticulously scrutinizes claim data to uncover irregularities and potential fraud indicators, enabling prompt detection of suspicious claims. Additionally, by automating fraud detection processes, the system streamlines claim processing, expedites legitimate claims, and enhances overall customer satisfaction.

Looking ahead, the future prospects of a Vehicle Insurance Claim Fraud Detection system are highly promising. As advancements in machine learning and data analysis persist,

the system can undergo further refinement to enhance its precision and effectiveness. By training on extensive datasets, it can refine its ability to discern subtle fraud patterns. Moreover, integration with external data sources, such as social media and law enforcement databases, offers the opportunity for deeper insights and a more comprehensive understanding of claim contexts

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Reddy, R. Singh and A. Agarwal, "Fraud Detection in Insurance Claims using Machine Learning," 2020 IEEE International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Automation (ICCCA), 2020.
- [2] V. R. Prabhu, A. R. Kulkarni, S. K. Varghese and M. R. Shenoy, "Insurance Claim Fraud Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms," 2020 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Advanced Computing and Communication (ISPACC), 2020.
- [3] A. K. Sharma, S. Pal, S. V. Gheewala and A. Jain, "Detection and Prediction of Insurance Fraud Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence & IoT (ICCIoT), 2021.
- [4] S. B. Somwanshi, S. M. T. Javed and S. V. Dev, "Fraud Detection in Insurance Sector Using Machine Learning Techniques," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Computing and Communication Technologies (CONECCT), 2021.
- [5] R. Sharma, P. Singh, A. R. Swami and N. Rastogi, "Deep Learning Based Fraud Detection in Insurance Sector," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Sustainable Systems (ICISS), 2021.
- [6] S. Gupta, V. Chandra and S. Chatterjee, "Insurance Fraud Detection Using Machine Learning," 2021 3rd International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication Control and Networking (ICACCCN), 2021.
- [7] S. R. Aher, S. D. Kulkarni and N. V. Pawar, "Fraud Detection in Insurance Sector Using Machine Learning Techniques," 2022 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Computing and Communication Technologies (CONECCT), 2022.
- [8] A. G. Pawar, V. G. Malviya and R. R. Thakare, "Machine Learning Techniques for Fraud Detection in Insurance Sector," 2022 IEEE International Conference on Power, Control, Signals and Systems (ICPCSS), 2022.
- [9] R. Kumar, S. Kumar, S. Sharma and R. Kumar, "Fraud Detection in Insurance Sector Using Machine Learning Algorithms," 2023 IEEE International Conference on Advances in Electrical Engineering (ICAEE), 2023.
- [10] N. Agrawal, S. Gupta, V. Saxena and S. Kumar, "Insurance Claim Fraud Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence & IoT (ICCIoT), 2024.